

1 **Beyond Oxygen Fugacity: A Compositional Metric to probe Earth's Redox Structure**

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4 **Abstract**

5 **We quantify the redox capacity (dO_2) by redox titration —a measure of the quantity of oxygen**
6 **required to fully oxidize a sample —for rocks spanning Earth's upper mantle to surface sediments.**
7 **Values span three orders of magnitude, with the greatest variability in metamorphic and surface**
8 **rocks that host both highly reduced (rich in carbon and sulfur) and highly oxidized materials. In**
9 **contrast, exhumed lower crustal and mantle rocks display more uniform values of dO_2 . This**
10 **distribution reflects not a progressive, net planetary oxidation, but active redox *partitioning*,**
11 **structured by far-from-equilibrium biological chemistry, surface processes, and tectonic cycling.**
12 **Unlike thermodynamic potentials (μO_2), the compositional variable dO_2 directly captures the**
13 **shallow Earth's redox structure. This framework provides an experimentally grounded, physically**
14 **intuitive metric for quantifying redox transfers and assessing their geophysical consequences.**

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19 Plain language summary

20 We measured the redox capacity (dO_2)—how much oxygen is needed to oxidize the rock—across
21 Earth's upper mantle, crust, and surface sediment samples. Our results show extreme variations, with
22 surface and metamorphic rocks hosting both highly reduced (carbon/sulfur-rich) and oxidized materials,
23 a stunning heterogeneity. In contrast, deeper rocks from the lower crust and mantle are more uniform.
24 This patchwork isn't produced by slow, steady oxidation of the planet but by an active biosphere and
25 plate tectonics that continuously recycle oxygen. By using the variable dO_2 (a compositional measure)
26 instead of traditional oxygen potential (μO_2), we reveal a clearer picture of Earth's shallow redox
27 structure.

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36 Introduction

37 Oxygen governs fundamental Earth processes, from mantle melting to biogeochemical cycling, yet the
38 distribution of redox-sensitive elements that control its circulation remains poorly constrained (Frost
39 and McCammon, 2008; Kasting et al., 1993). These elements—primarily carbon, iron, sulfur, hydrogen,
40 and manganese—determine the microscopic redox state of rocks and sediments, but also the
41 distribution of reduced and oxidized domains on Earth, ie. its macroscopic redox structure. Redox-
42 sensitive elements exhibit variable oxidation states, making their quantification both challenging and
43 incomplete without precise speciation data. Although these elements often constitute a small fraction
44 of a rock composition, they are key inputs in thermodynamic models of the Earth interior for assessing
45 its geophysical properties (Connolly and Cesare, 1993; Frost and McCammon, 2008).

46 Traditional methods often rely on thermodynamic or compositional proxies to assess the redox state of
47 rocks, but each has significant drawbacks. First, while oxygen fugacity (fO_2) is rigorously defined in
48 equilibrium thermodynamics ($fO_2 = fO_2^\circ \exp[(\mu O_2 - gO_2^\circ)/RT]$, where gO_2° is the standard molar Gibbs
49 energy of pure O_2 at 1 bar and temperature of interest, T (Eugster, 1957), and fO_2° is the fugacity of the
50 reference standard state, ie. 1 bar), it describes a redox ‘driving force’ at equilibrium under specific P - T
51 conditions, not bulk oxygen transfers (Connolly and Cesare, 1993). For instance, the $\Delta \log fO_2$ (difference
52 between $\log fO_2$ of the rock and $\log fO_2$ of the fayalite-magnetite-quartz buffer (FMQ), $\log fO_2^{FMQ}$) from the
53 lower mantle (FMQ-5 to FMQ-4 (Rohrbach and Schmidt, 2011)) to the upper mantle/crust (FMQ+2
54 (McCammon, 2005)) primarily reflects structural transformations in redox-sensitive mineral phases
55 rather than bulk oxygen content (Frost and McCammon, 2008). As a consequence, fO_2 can be constant
56 in low-variance mineral assemblages, such as the magnetite–hematite buffer, even when Fe oxidation
57 states in the assemblage vary ($Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$). This phenomenon obscures redox heterogeneities critical to
58 petrology and biogeochemistry. Second, proxies like $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ ratios (Alt and Honnorez, 1984; Stolper
59 and Keller, 2018) or redox budget (RB) (Evans, 2006) enable mass transfer estimates, but require
60 analytically-intensive speciation techniques (XANES, Mössbauer spectroscopy (Cottrell and Kelley,

61 2011; O'Neill et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018)). This complexity has limited their widespread application.
62 Third, these methods are often element-specific, typically relying on assumptions or scaling model to
63 account for other redox carriers (e.g. H, C, S) (Brounce et al., 2019; Canfield, 2004; Evans, 2012; Galvez,
64 2020). Collectively, these thermodynamic limitations, experimental complexities, or compositional
65 bias calls for a universal, measurable metric to quantify the heterogeneous distribution of oxygen across
66 Earth's reservoirs.

67 In this context, we have presented a direct experimental approach to quantify the specific redox capacity
68 (dO_2), defined as (Galvez and Jaccard, 2021)

$$69 \quad dO_2 = (1/2 \times \text{Total O consumed (mol)}) / (\text{Sample mass (g)})$$

70 This metric quantifies the oxygen required to fully oxidize all redox-sensitive elements (primarily H, C, S,
71 Fe and Mn) in 1 g of material to their highest oxidation state, a redox titration. Unlike fO_2 , however, dO_2
72 offers three main advantages: (i) it is experimentally measurable without prior speciation data, (ii) it
73 applies to both equilibrium and non-equilibrium systems, and (iii) enables for consistent comparison
74 across surface or deep geologic reservoirs. Using this experimental approach, we present the first
75 comprehensive dO_2 database spanning a wide range of geologic materials. High-precision titration of 42
76 representative samples reveals a striking three-order-of-magnitude redox dichotomy, characteristic of
77 the shallow lithosphere. Organic-rich sediments exhibit dO_2 values exceeding 100 mmol/g, whereas
78 igneous and metamorphic lithospheric rocks display dO_2 values below 250 $\mu\text{mol/g}$. This compositional
79 contrast reflects a dynamic O_2 partitioning driven by biological activity, sedimentary cycling, and
80 metasomatic processes. The intuitive and compositional nature of dO_2 bridges petrology and
81 biogeochemistry. Notably, this metric is compatible with phase equilibria modelling, enabling
82 quantitative assessment of redox-driven geophysical processes.

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84 **Methods**

85 *Redox Titration Protocol*

86 Samples were ground to <100 μm and homogenized to ensure uniform composition. Aliquots (10–50
87 mg) were loaded into quartz tubes together with an excess of CuO (serving as an oxygen donor), flame-
88 sealed under vacuum (~5 μbar), and heated to 900°C for 10 hours. This temperature ensured complete
89 oxidation of redox-sensitive elements (H, C, S, Fe) under conditions maintained by the CuO-Cu redox
90 couple:

92 Oxygen fugacity was buffered at $\approx 5 \times 10^{-5}$ bar, calculated using NIST-JANAF data [Chase, 1998], and
93 typically reached within minutes. Additionally, we introduce Mg(OH)₂ as a sulfur getter (Fig. 1A),
94 facilitating the complete oxidation of sulfur to Mg-sulfate (MgSO₄). Complete oxidation in these
95 experimental conditions means C, S and Fe reach the maximal C⁴⁺, S⁶⁺ and Fe³⁺ oxidation state. In
96 samples with sluggish oxidation kinetics, we first homogenized them with a 12:22
97 metaborate/tetraborate flux before insertion in an inert platinum or gold tube (Fig 1A). This novel
98 procedure promotes eutectic melting of the sample and flux at around 800 °C, enabling full oxidation
99 within 10 hours, even for highly refractory mineral standards such as almandine (Fig. 1B). Post-reaction,
100 oxygen consumption, $n\text{O}(\text{mol}) = (w^f - w^i) / M_{\text{O}}$, was determined gravimetrically from the weight loss of CuO
101 in the inner capsule ($(w^f - w^i)$, Table S1). Redox capacity—Absolute (ΔO_2) and specific ($d\text{O}_2$)—was
102 derived as:

103 $\Delta\text{O}_2 = 1/2 \times n\text{O} (\text{mol})$ (3)

104 $d\text{O}_2 = \Delta\text{O}_2 (\text{mol}) / \text{Sample mass (g)}$ (4)

105 Background values remained below 500 nmol O₂, with analytical reproducibility better than 5%. The
106 almandine crystals were sourced from garnet-bearing dacite at El Hoyazo, Spain (courtesy of Peter
107 Ulmer (Ulmer et al., 2018)). Note that $d\text{O}_2$ designates the ‘O₂-equivalent’ component, not the molecular
108 dioxygen species, hence representing half the total amount of oxygen consumed per gram of sample.

109 The speciation of oxygen at 900°C and 5 μbar in the gas phase, or in the sample, is thermodynamically
110 and analytically irrelevant.

111 *Sample Collection and Preparation*

112 The dataset comprises 42 samples from Earth's upper mantle to surface sediments from the collections
113 of the University of Lausanne and ETH Zurich (Table S1). Rather than aiming for a statistically
114 representative crustal average, which would require broader sampling, the selection focuses on
115 capturing redox extremes that serve to draw a macroscopic picture of lithospheric redox structure, and
116 show the usefulness of the new metric. Mafic/ultramafic rocks include basalts, dunites (Kohistan), and
117 hornblendites. The metasedimentary rocks comprise graphitic schists (Alpine Corsica), calcschists
118 (Western Alps), and micaschists. Surface materials include organic-rich soils (Cameroon), Monterey
119 Bay bitumen, and black shales (Green River, Messel).

120 Nominal estimates of dO_2 values were also calculated to contextualize our measurements (Table S2).
121 The dO_2 values of hydrothermally altered mafic rocks were estimated using published $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ ratios
122 (Alt and Honnorez, 1984; Cottrell and Kelley, 2011), and the dO_2 values of marine sediments from
123 DSDP718 (Bengal fan), DSDP126 (Aegean sea), DSDP173 (East Pacific, California), ODP167 (Juan de
124 Fuca), were obtained from published organic carbon/sulfur concentrations (Clift, 2017), assuming C^{4+}
125 and S^{+1} speciations. Average values for unaltered oceanic crust ($dO_2^{maf} \approx 290 \mu\text{mol/g}$) were calculated
126 based on published Fe^{2+} (5.6 wt%) and S^{-1} (0.08 wt%) averages (Evans, 2012; Galvez, 2020).

127 **Results**

128 Figure 2 highlights the pronounced redox heterogeneity across surface and shallow subsurface
129 reservoirs. Measured dO_2 values span over four orders of magnitude, ranging from just 220 μmol/g in
130 oxidized Moroccan phosphorites (#24, #25—the lowest values in the dataset) to as high as $\sim 9.8 \times 10^4$
131 μmol/g in bitumen from Monterey Bay (#12) and biological resins (#1). Intermediate values ($1\text{--}5 \times 10^4$
132 μmol/g) were measured in a representative tropical organic-rich soil from Cameroon (#2), an organic-
133 rich reference lake sediment (17 wt% organic matter, #3), and in a suite of unextracted shales

134 (Westfield, New Albany, Messel, Aleksinal, Autun, Ohio, and Green River; #17, 19–23, courtesy of Tim
135 Eglinton). These shales and soil samples retain substantial quantities of biogenic reductants, including
136 C and S in diverse oxidation states. In contrast, all reference samples for marine sediments and
137 estuarine muds (#4–9) yielded values in the 500–2,000 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ range. Highly oxidized stream sediments
138 and soils (#10, #11) define the lower end of our dataset.

139 In contrast to surface sediments, igneous or deep crustal rocks display a markedly narrower range of
140 $d\text{O}_2$ values. They span from 138 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ in a garnet hornblendite from Kohistan (#37) to 700 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ in a
141 spinel-clinopyroxenite from the same region (#38). Our ultramafic rocks – including certified reference
142 material NIM-D and dunites from Kohistan- along with basalts and gabbros (standards JGB-2 (#35) and
143 STA BIR-1A (#33)), fall within a tightly constrained range of 250–350 $\mu\text{mol/g}$.

144 Metasedimentary rocks (calcschists, #26–31; micaschist SDC-1, #32) exhibit a wide spectrum of $d\text{O}_2$
145 values falling between those of mafic and surface datasets, from 200 to 9,114 $\mu\text{mol O}_2/\text{g}$. It reflects the
146 partial preservation of organic C and S, the presence of sulfides, and/or postdepositional metasomatic
147 redistribution of C and S (Galvez et al., 2013).

148 Figure 3 illustrates the effect of oxidative alteration, which decreases the $d\text{O}_2$ values for hydrothermally
149 altered rocks (Alt and Honnorez, 1984), between 150–200 $\mu\text{mol/g}$, with respect to the unaltered mafic
150 average $d\text{O}_2^{\text{maf}} = 290 \mu\text{mol/g}$ (method). The decline reflects Fe-silicates and sulfide oxidation. A similar
151 trend is observed for serpentized peridotites (Fig. 3). The results demonstrate that the oxidative impact
152 of deep-sea hydrothermalism is therefore clearly resolvable by $d\text{O}_2$ measurements.

153 Overall, the three-order-of-magnitude range in $d\text{O}_2$ values underscores a fundamental redox dichotomy.
154 The surface environment exhibits extreme heterogeneities, driven by biogeochemical cycling that
155 concentrates reductants like organic carbon and sulfur. In contrast, the lithosphere displays more
156 limited redox variability, resulting from longer-term tectonic and metasomatic homogenization and
157 mineralogies dominated by Fe-silicates and sulfides.

158 **Discussion**

159 **1. dO_2 vs. fO_2 , characterizing Earth's dichotomous redox structure**

160 The three-order-of-magnitude range in dO_2 reflects an heterogeneity that fO_2 cannot resolve, for the
161 latter reflects thermodynamic potential (μ_{O_2}) rather than bulk electron transfer (Connolly and Cesare,
162 1993). But other metrics, such as redox budget (RB), could, in principle, quantify this heterogeneity
163 (Evans, 2006, 2012). A significant focus of the RB literature, in particular, has been on the *extensive*
164 nature of this property—a system's variable depending on system size—and its distinction from
165 *intensive* potentials like fO_2 (Brounce et al., 2019; Evans, 2006; Maffei et al., 2024). However, this focus
166 has overshadowed both its principal strength—that it is a compositional variable independent of
167 thermodynamic equilibrium requirements, regardless of its intensive or extensive nature—and its more
168 critical practical challenge: its reliance on analytically demanding measurements (or assumptions) of
169 elemental speciation (e.g., $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$, carbon and sulfur speciation (Cottrell and Kelley, 2011; Wilke et al.,
170 2001).

171 In this context, the dO_2 has the strengths of being a compositional variable—defined as a ratio of
172 extensive quantities (Connolly, 1990; Hillert, 1985; Palatnik and Landau, 1964)—, and it bypasses the
173 speciation problem by measuring the integrated redox state directly experimentally under rigorous
174 conditions. This distinguishes it from both $Fe^{3+}/\Sigma Fe$ ratios (Jenner et al., 2015; Wilke et al., 2001) or RB
175 (Evans, 2006) at a fundamental level, and makes it complementary to fO_2 .

176 This is clearly illustrated by a classic case of redox partitioning in Alpine Corsica (Table S1) where
177 serpentinites ($dO_2 \sim 250 \mu\text{mol/g}$; $\log fO_2 \sim \text{FMQ}-4$) interacted with adjacent siliceous marbles ($dO_2 \sim 500-$
178 $1000 \mu\text{mol/g}$) under blueschist-facies conditions (Chopin et al., 2008; Galvez et al., 2013). The
179 serpentinites' lower fO_2 drove carbonate reduction in the marbles, forming a graphitic aureole and raising
180 the marble dO_2 to $>9,114 \mu\text{mol/g}$ (Table 1). This stark contrast highlights that fO_2 dictates reaction
181 directionality at a given pressure and temperature condition, while dO_2 quantifies cumulative electron
182 transfer associated with the redistribution of redox sensitive elements. But the compositional nature of

183 dO_2 also enables computing the relative masses (ΔM^{rock}) of reacting rocks to produce the reaction
184 aureole, a useful and novel insight. For example, assuming the serpentinite is fully oxidized after reaction
185 ($dO_2 \rightarrow 0$) and applying the mass balance $\Delta M^{\text{rock}} = (dO_2^{\text{final, sed}} - dO_2^{\text{initial, sed}}) / dO_2^{\text{initial, serp}}$ indicates that the
186 reacting serpentinite mass was at least $\approx(9000-1000)/250 \approx 32$ times that of the marble, a minimum
187 estimate as the serpentinite was not fully oxidized (Malvoisin et al., 2017; Malvoisin et al., 2012).

188 **2. dO_2 's Predictive Power in Modeling**

189 The dO_2 metric also enables for more intuitive computational modeling because it is designed to
190 integrate naturally into Gibbs energy minimization approaches (e.g., Perple_X (Connolly, 2005)). In
191 computational thermodynamics, petrological systems are defined by a set of components like SiO_2 and
192 FeO , plus a mobile redox O_2 component to account for the formation of higher order oxides such as
193 Fe_2O_3 , according to mass and equilibrium constraints. The dO_2 metric fits directly into this framework,
194 as it provides a compositional constraint on redox state that is independent of prior speciation
195 knowledge. This can be illustrated in a simplified Fe-only system, where the stoichiometry of oxidation
196 ($4 FeO + O_2 = 2 Fe_2O_3$) defines the relation:

$$197 \Delta O_2 = \frac{1}{4} n(FeO)$$

198 where ΔO_2 stands for the absolute redox capacity (eq. 3). The thermodynamic component (O_2^{thermo}) is
199 more commonly related to the oxidized iron component, although it is not an obligation, via:

$$200 n(O_2)^{\text{thermo}} = \frac{1}{2} n(Fe_2O_3)$$

201 Combining this with the total iron balance ($FeO^{\text{tot}} = FeO + 2 Fe_2O_3$) show how ΔO_2 can be related to the
202 conventional O_2^{thermo} component:

$$203 n(O_2)^{\text{thermo}} = \frac{1}{4} n(FeO)^{\text{tot}} - \Delta O_2$$

204 This enables phase equilibrium calculations using standard bulk composition data and dO_2 , without prior
205 knowledge of Fe speciation. For example, in basalt BE_N (#34) (11.9 wt% FeO^{tot} (Govindaraju, 1980)), a
206 measured dO_2 of 284 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ predicts 4.16 wt% Fe_2O_3 (wt% $Fe_2O_3 \approx 0.016 \times dO_2$ ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)), consistent
207 with independent estimates ($Fe_2O_3 \approx 4$ wt%). Using this input in thermodynamic software (e.g., Perple_X

208 (Connolly, 2009)) yields any relevant system properties; for BE_N, equilibrium f_{O_2} , $\log f_{O_2} = -12$ kJ/mol
209 at 30 kbar and 800 °C, and $\log f_{O_2} \approx -19$ kJ/mol at 10 kbar and 600 °C.

210

211 3. From Bulk Capacity to Differential Response

212 The dO_2 provides a robust measure of total oxygen demand (Fig. 1), but two interesting challenges
213 remain: (1) deconvolving the individual contributions of redox-sensitive elements (H, C, S, Fe, Mn) to the
214 bulk dO_2 signal, and (2) quantifying the system's responsiveness to redox perturbations, which dO_2 alone
215 does not capture. Addressing these challenges calls for complementary properties—response
216 functions—that complete a triad of redox metrics: capacity (dO_2), driving force (f_{O_2}), and buffer capacity.

217 We first define the isothermal redox susceptibility:

$$219 \quad \vartheta_{\mu} = \left(\frac{dn_{O_2}}{d\mu_{O_2}} \right)_{P,T}$$

218 Redox susceptibility can be estimated using thermodynamic software.

220 At first-order phase boundaries, such as the magnetite-hematite transition, ϑ_{μ} diverges ($\vartheta_{\mu} \rightarrow \infty$), marking
221 a phase transition where an infinitesimal change in μ_{O_2} drives a finite reaction. Experimentally, it
222 corresponds to constructing a full adsorption/absorption isotherm in a gas mixing furnace, by measuring
223 the oxygen uptake n_{O_2} versus μ_{O_2} (or $\log(P_{O_2})$) at elevated temperatures. Conversely, the total redox
224 capacity ΔO_2 can then be recovered via piecewise integration of the susceptibility curve from the
225 sample's initial state to a fully oxidized reference state.

226 Another experimentally accessible parameter is the thermal redox response:

227

$$228 \quad \vartheta_T = \left(\frac{dn_{O_2}}{dT} \right)_{P,T}$$

229

230 This can be measured via controlled thermal ramping with gas analysis at constant elevated pO_2 , thereby
231 bypassing the challenges of equilibrium measurements. At low T , kinetic limitations smear phase
232 transitions, producing finite, integrable peaks in θ_T . The integral of this function yields the total ΔO_2
233 change, while their shape provides as a thermodynamic and kinetic fingerprint of a sample's *oxidability*,
234 constraining activation energies and reaction mechanisms.

235 Thermal ramping also helps resolve the contributions of different redox-sensitive elements to the bulk
236 dO_2 signal by isolating temperature windows for the combustion of various redox carriers (e.g., organic
237 C, sulfides, ferrous Fe). Differential scanning calorimetry could provide further insights by detecting
238 enthalpy changes associated with redox reactions involving C, S, or Fe species with Cu. If these reactions
239 occur at distinct temperature ranges, each might produce a unique peak on a thermogram. By
240 determining or calibrating the enthalpy changes for these individual reactions, and integrating this data
241 with ΔO_2 measurements obtained simultaneously, it may be possible to distinguish and analyze the
242 contributions of each reaction, even when their temperature ranges overlap. These experimental
243 approaches are currently under development (Wu et al., in prep). Isotopic tracers, such as ^{18}O -enriched
244 CuO or O_2 gas, can add further resolution. For example, this might distinguish H_2O released from clays
245 versus $H_2^{18}O$ from H_2 or CH_4 oxidation, or separate unlabeled CO_2 from carbonate decomposition above
246 $600^\circ C$ from $C^{18}O_2$ produced by graphite oxidation in the same temperature range (Galvez et al., 2020).

247 Therefore, integrating *differential response functions* such as θ_μ and θ_T (Fig. 4), transforms dO_2 from a
248 static measure of oxygen demand into a fingerprint of redox state and response.

249

250 **4. Geological Implications**

251 Although limited in scope, our dataset allows for the exploration of a few geological implications, ranging
252 from subduction-related redox fluxes, and oxygen partitioning on primitive Earth O_2 , to the planetary
253 scale redox signatures of biological activity.

254 **Subduction fluxes**

255 The high dO_2 values measured in sediments (1300 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ [500–5000], Table S1) open the door to a re-
256 evaluation of subduction's role in the global redox cycle. For example, scaling these sediment dO_2 values
257 to global subducted sediment fluxes (1.73 [1.4–2.1] Pg yr^{-1} ; (Evans, 2012)) yields an estimated global
258 net O_2 output to the atmosphere via reductant subduction of approximately 2.25 $\text{Tmol } O_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ [0.70–
259 10.5], which is consistent with previous estimates (Galvez, 2020; Hayes and Waldbauer, 2006), and just
260 sufficient to counterbalance weathering sinks of O_2 to sustain long-term atmospheric oxygen steady-
261 state in the last 50 Myr (Galvez, 2020). While provisional, this estimate underscores a critical
262 shortcoming in current models of subduction redox cycling: they largely rely on Fe speciation
263 measurements (Brounce et al., 2019; Evans, 2012) and modelling approaches (Maffei et al., 2024;
264 Piccoli et al., 2019) that either rely heavily on fO_2 -derived thermodynamics, or demand compositional
265 constraints functionally equivalent to dO_2 (Connolly and Cesare, 1993). Our approach helps bridge this
266 gap by enabling a combination of dO_2 -based mass balances with thermodynamic modeling, offering a
267 unified framework to trace oxygen in subduction zones. Future research could test this through time-
268 resolved dO_2 analysis of IODP/ODP core (Brounce et al., 2019), minimizing reliance on speciation
269 assumptions and enabling resolution of temporal and regional variability in subduction zone redox
270 fluxes.

271 ***Pre-GOE Oxygen Production vs. Accumulation***

272 Next, the dO_2 metric may offer a novel means to quantitatively constrain oxygen dynamics predating the
273 Great Oxidation Event (GOE, 2.4 Ga). While the GOE marks the emergence of persistently oxygenated
274 atmosphere, geochemical evidence indicates that oxygenic photosynthesis arose earlier (~2.7 Ga) [e.g.
275 (Lyons et al., 2014), but see (Johnson et al., 2013) for debate]. This temporal offset has generated
276 competing models for Archean redox conditions, ranging from proposals of widespread oxic surface
277 environments (Ohmoto, 1998; Ohmoto et al., 2006), to globally anoxic conditions (Farquhar et al., 2011),
278 and the existence localized oxygen oases (Anbar et al., 2007; Olson et al., 2013).

279 Our work provides a pathway to resolve this debate by distinguishing between O₂ production and
280 accumulation. The dO_2 framework enables direct quantification of the oxygen production term, rather
281 than relying solely on discrete thresholds for oxygen accumulation in the ocean/atmosphere using
282 isotopic proxies. For example, using the IFP 160000 shale standard (TOC = 3.28 ± 0.14 wt%, dO_2 = 3.3–
283 3.7 mmol/g; this study) as a reference, we might estimate dO_2 values for Precambrian shales (1-5 wt%
284 TOC, (Husson and Peters, 2017; Wronkiewicz and Condie, 1987)), assuming a dO_2 /TOC relationship
285 similar to that of the IFP reference for simplicity: $dO_2 \approx 1.07\text{--}5.33$ mmol/g. Combined with existing
286 estimates of shale mass and TOC, this framework enables regional or global quantification of O₂
287 production rates from preserved geological archives, before direct measurements of those vast
288 collections of Archean shales can be completed.

289

290 ***Abiotic vs biotic O₂ distribution***

291 Finally, our dataset might offer insight into planetary signatures. Earth's surface exhibits a striking three-
292 order-of-magnitude dO_2 contrast, a redox structure shaped by both biology and tectonics. High- dO_2
293 sediments record biological cycling, while low- dO_2 lithospheric rocks reflect geological homogenization
294 and partitioning over long timescales. This polarity is absent in abiotic systems. For instance,
295 photochemical O₂ production (e.g., via H₂O dissociation) can oxidize planetary surfaces, but in the
296 absence of biological feedbacks and plate tectonics, reductants are progressively lost to space (Hall et
297 al., 1998), resulting in a system with no dynamic redox reciprocity (Falkowski and Godfrey, 2008).

298 In contrast, Earth's redox landscape *as we know it* is both extreme and *symmetric*: oxidized and reduced
299 phases coexist at macroscopic scales (Figs. 2, 4), reflecting a closed-loop system where oxygen and
300 reductants are not only retained, but actively partitioned, and recycled simultaneously. This duality is a
301 direct manifestation of the interplay of biology and tectonics—a feedback mechanism absent on abiotic
302 worlds. While net planetary oxidation does occur on Earth today, its influence during the Phanerozoic is
303 marginal (Catling and Kasting, 2017).

304 The defining signature of Earth's biosphere is not, therefore, simply the presence of oxygen, but the
305 spatial and chemical *gradients* it generates. We propose that this extreme redox symmetry—
306 characterized by the juxtaposition of high- dO_2 domains (shales, soils, S-rich sediments) and low- dO_2
307 domains (carbonates, basalts, mantle rocks) (Fig. 3, Table S1) constitutes a quantifiable and mappable
308 biosignature. Not merely the signature of oxygen, but a signature of its *dynamic coupling* to reductants
309 across geological and environmental scales.

310 **Conclusion**

311 We demonstrate that the dO_2 metric provides a direct, experimentally robust measure of redox capacity
312 that overcomes key limitations of traditional redox proxies. By integrating the total oxygen demand
313 across all redox-sensitive elements without relying on speciation data, dO_2 captures electron transfers
314 inaccessible to equilibrium-based metrics (fO_2). Our results reveal a three-order-of-magnitude contrast
315 between biologically influenced surface reservoirs and tectonically homogenized lithospheric rocks.

316 This compositional metric offers a new approach for modeling redox-driven processes in both the
317 surface and deep Earth. dO_2 complements fO_2 by quantifying the extent of redox reactions, while fO_2
318 dictates their direction. Together, they reveal a heterogeneous lithospheric redox structure shaped by:
319 (1) far-from-equilibrium biological cycling, (2) tectonic redox partitioning, and (3) near-equilibrium
320 mantle buffering. Thus, dO_2 emerges not just as a practical analytical tool, but as a diagnostic feature of
321 Earth as a biologically and tectonically modulated planet.

322 Looking ahead, extending of this framework to include response functions such as the redox
323 susceptibility and its kinetic counterpart will soon allow us to move beyond bulk capacity to characterize
324 the dynamic response of Earth materials to redox perturbations - a material *redox fingerprint*. This opens
325 new avenues for quantifying reaction kinetics, disequilibrium processes, and the timescales of redox
326 transformations across diverse geologic environments.

327

328 **Captions**

329 Figure 1. A. Experimental set-up with outer Silica tubes, inner CuO capsule and gold/platinum capsules.
330 B. Fractional redox capacity at time t , $rO_{2,t} = dO_{2,t} / dO_{2,f}$, where $dO_{2,t}$ is the specific redox capacity at time
331 t , and $dO_{2,f}$ is the specific redox capacity after full oxidation. Sample MSG9, a shale from Monte San
332 Giorgio in the Swiss Alps, and almandine (garnet) from dacite of El Hoyazo, Spain (courtesy Peter Ulmer),
333 are completely oxidized after 10 hours. Complete oxidation of the garnet is achieved by melting the
334 sample under vacuum, in an open gold tube, and under the oxidizing atmosphere of our nominal
335 experimental setup (Fig. 1).

336 Figure 2. Results of dO_2 values measured in various rocks and sediments sampled at the Earth's surface.
337 Numbering corresponds to experiment numbers and conditions detailed in Table S1.

338 Figure 3. Comparison of dO_2 values measured (filled symbols), and nominal (calculated, not measured)
339 estimates (empty symbols). Samples from the shallow surface and subsurface (soils/ unconsolidated
340 sediments (pale yellow), shales and kerogens (black)) are clearly distinguished from samples
341 representing the crystalline lithosphere (metamorphic rocks, basalts, ultramafics). Empty symbols
342 represent nominal estimated redox capacity values computed from Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} compositions of altered
343 mafic (Alt and Honnorez, 1984) and ultramafic rocks (Cottrell and Kelley, 2011; Evans, 2012). Unaltered
344 ultramafic values are from (Cottrell and Kelley, 2011) while altered ultramafic values are from (Cottrell
345 and Kelley, 2011), or from total organic C (assumed to be elemental C) and total S (assumed to be S^{-1})
346 from deep sea sediments (IODP and DSDP data in (Clift, 2017)). Oxidative weathering drives the values
347 toward lower dO_2 , making the rocks more 'oxidized'. Addition of reductants such as C and S drives values
348 toward more elevated dO_2 higher than the mafic average (cf Method section).

349 Figure 4. A. H loss from photochemical dissociation of H_2O is a common phenomenon on telluric planets.
350 In this process, O_2 may be transiently stabilized in atmosphere, leading some to debate the possibility of
351 false positives of biogenicity (Harman et al., 2015; Reinhard et al., 2017). This process leads to the loss
352 of reductive equivalents to space, with the oxidant left to accumulate at the planet's surface. The
353 accumulation of oxidants at the planet's surface, leading to its net oxidation is illustrated in panel B. By

354 contrast, the process we describe here is internal in that both oxidants and reductants are produced in
355 equivalent quantities, and both are simultaneously accumulating. The accumulation may not occur in
356 the same reservoirs, producing a redox differentiation which has no effect on the overall oxidation state
357 of the planet. This scenario, broadly defined as a 'planetary disproportionation', is characterized by the
358 accumulation of both oxidants and reductants, allowing for the co-existence of redox extremes in the
359 same planetary reservoirs.

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362 **OPEN RESEARCH/AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

363 Data archiving is underway, in Zenodo. The redox capacity data used for this study are available at Zenodo
364 via [10.5281/zenodo.14506083](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506083).

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366 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

367 The authors have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

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385 Figure 1

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402 Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4.

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588 Supporting Information for

589 **Beyond Oxygen Fugacity: A Compositional Metric to probe Earth's Redox Structure**

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592

593

594 **Contents of this file**

595

596 Tables S1 to S2

597

598 **Introduction**

599 • These two supplementary tables contain the measurements (Table S1) and calculations
600 (based on literature bulk rock data) of redox capacities.

601

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605 **Table S1.** Redox capacity measured by redox titration.

606 **Table S2.** Nominal estimates of dO_2 values from literature compilations.

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